

RATIONALISING THE LOCATION AND DESIGN OF THE WASTE DUMP IN THE CASE OF OPEN-PIT MINING

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ABSTRACT. The location for dumping the waste from the open-pit mine has a significant weight for the establishment of the waste treatment costs. According to the constructive parameters of the waste dump and the terrain's characteristics, the volume of the affected area is determined, in relation to the waste volume generated from the exploitation of a mineral deposit. In order to optimise the waste dump's location and its constructive parameters, a number of alternatives have to be taken into account. These alternatives have to be technically plausible, as well as their safety factor must be satisfactory. Based on the considered alternatives, the optimisation problem can be defined so that the optimal solution provides the required capacity of the waste dump, as well as a minimal area of negative environmental impact and lowest operational costs.

Keywords: waste dump, optimisation, location, costs

Introduction

Waste dumping of the overburden in open-pit mining tends to be a topical problem all around the world due to the long term impact on the environment. In order to ensure a suitable site for waste (overburden) dumping, certain areas have to be obtained from the state or from their private owners. These areas are usually either forested, fertile lands (sometimes used for agricultural purposes) or infertile lands. Nevertheless, due to the accelerated environmental policy on a world-wide scale and the intense growth of the responsibilities which mining companies have to take, the overburden treatment problem tends to be more complex than decades ago. Undoubtedly, the negative environmental impact from waste dumping has to be minimal. At the same time the operational costs for waste dumps building have to be minimal too which sometimes conflicts with the minimal environmental impact goal. Therefore, a certain balance has to be achieved in order to satisfy the specific environmental requirements for the region, where the open-pit mining takes place, as well as to minimise the transportation costs, operational costs for waste treatment (Aleksandrova, 1998) and their respective auxiliary operations costs.

Analyses show that during the exploitation of a certain deposit the overall costs for overburden treatment tend to be approximately 10 – 12% from the total operational costs for open-pit mining (Atanasov et al., 2001). Therefore, optimising this group of operational costs will lead to an increased profit for the mining companies. Due to the improved capabilities of mining software products and their options for automated waste dump designs, many design alternatives can be generated for a shorter time, which would lead to more rational and reasonable decisions when choosing the final waste dump design. This could lead not only to the improvement of the economic impact of the waste dumping, but the scale of waste dumping as well and therefore the scale of the environmental impact.

Rationalising the waste dumping solution

Let there be N considered alternatives for areas, where the overburden from the open-pit mine could be dumped. These areas have to be considered according to the specific terrain inside the claimed area, acquired from the state. An alternative

which is considered feasible is the one which follows each of these key requirements:

- 1) it is not placed outside the claimed area from the mining company;
- 2) it is not placed on areas, which will compromise the environment's water sources;
- 3) it is not placed on weak soil which will compromise the dump stability;
- 4) it is not placed near roads and buildings, which may become compromised.

Depending on the type of extracted mineral resource, further conditions may be adopted as well. Nonetheless, every feasible area for waste dumping can vary depending on their rationality. The most rational places where waste dumping can take place are concave land forms, due to the improved stability of the dump as well as their ability to accumulate higher amounts of waste volume. Plain terrain could also be used for waste dumping due to its easy access. Convex land forms also prove to be feasible for waste dumping, however, the terrain slope has to be considered carefully. In addition, hillside dumping may prove to ensure the stability of the waste dump, it also reduces the overall volume the dump could accumulate (Atanasov et al., 2001).

Therefore, the N considered dump areas alternatives can include convex, concave land forms or plain terrain (natural and artificial) which fulfil all the environmental and legal requirements of the state. Each considered dump area can accumulate a certain amount of waste depending on the waste dump design.

In order to minimise the negative environmental impact, the total area used for waste dumping has to be minimal (Aleksandrova, 1999). This leads to several benefits – no additional forested or fertile areas have to be disturbed, as well as no further reclamation activities have to be made. From an economic point of view, waste dumping depends mostly on the distance of the dump from the open-pit mine and therefore an optimisation problem must be solved for the transportation costs (Ortiz, 2017).

In order to achieve a balance between the environmental impact of waste dumping process as well as the economic feasibility of the dump design, two target functions are defined:

$$F_1 = \sum_i^N C_{disi} + C_{tri} + C_{ci} + C_{reci} \rightarrow \min \quad (1)$$

$$F_2 = \sum_i^N S_i \rightarrow \min \quad (2)$$

where:

N – number of the considered areas, where waste dumping is acceptable;

i – the consecutive number of each considered area for waste dumping;

C_{disi} – total costs for disturbing the initial terrain, acquired for waste dumping in area i , USD (BGN);

C_{tri} – total costs for overburden transportation to area i , USD (BGN);

C_{ci} – total costs for waste dump construction in area i , USD (BGN);

C_{reci} – total costs for waste dump area reclamation i , USD (BGN);

$$F_1 = \sum_i^N C_{disi} + C_{tri} + C_{ci} + C_{reci} =$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \left\{ \left[\left(L_{ij} + \frac{K_{ijk} \cdot H + (k-1) \cdot H}{\sin \arctg i_s} + \overline{L}_{ijk} \right) \cdot \gamma_o \cdot c_{tr} + c_c \right] \cdot \left[K_{ijk} \cdot V_{ijk} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} V_{ijk'} \right] + \right.$$

$$\left. + \left[K_{ijk}^{dis} \cdot K_{ijk} \cdot V_{ijk} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} K_{ijk'}^{dis} \cdot V_{ijk'} \right] \cdot (c_{dis} + c_{rec}) \right\} \cdot X_{ijk}$$

where:

n_i – number of alternatives for construction of the waste dump at location i ;

j – serial number of the alternative to the construction of the dump;

A_{ij} – Boolean variable, taking into account the choice of a single alternative j for location i ;

m_j – number of dump benches for alternative j ;

k – consecutive number of the dump benches for alternative j ;

C_{dis} – relative costs for preparation of the area for the base of the dump, USD/m²;

c_{tr} – relative costs for transposing the overburden, USD/(t.km);

γ_o – bulk density of the overburden, t/m³;

L_{ij} – transport distance to dump location with design alternative j for location i , km;

K_{ijk} – coefficient of proportionality of the volume dumped at bench number k ;

H – height of the dump bench, m;

i_s – slope of the ramp connecting the dump benches, %;

\overline{L}_{ijk} – average transport distance for the k -th step of the j -th variant of the dump, located at location i , km;

p_u – relative costs for construction of the embankment, USD/m³;

V_{ijk} – volume of overburden in swollen state, necessary for construction of the k -th bench, m³;

$\sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} V_{ijk'}$ – volume of overburden in the swollen state,

necessary for the construction of the level $k-1$, m³;

S_i – disturbed area, required for building the base of the waste dump in area i , m².

Each considered area i can be used for developing n_i technologically feasible dump design alternatives, which are proven to pass a stability test (Hoek-Brown, Mohr-Coloumb, etc.)

The sum of the required areas for waste dumping can be calculated by the equation:

$$F_2 = \sum_i^N S_i =$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \left[K_{ijk}^{dis} \cdot K_{ijk} \cdot V_{ijk} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} K_{ijk'}^{dis} \cdot V_{ijk'} \right] \cdot X_{ijk}$$

The sum of the preliminary operations for preparing the waste dump area, transportation costs for the overburden, operational costs for waste dumping and the reclamation costs can be calculated with the general formula:

X_{ijk} – Boolean variable, taking into account the level to which the dump is constructed;

K_{ijk}^{dis} – factor taking into account the disturbing effect of the overburden from the k -th bench of alternative j for the dump, located at location i , m²/m³.

The K^{dis} factor takes into account the shape of the terrain on which the embankment is built. It is considered that a minimal negative impact on the environment is observed in case of violation of less amount of areas required for the waste dump construction. This factor is the reciprocal value of the capacity factor for the dumping area (Hristov and Aleksandrova, 2000). Therefore, the location of the dump is relative to the land shapes and the position of the dump will be more rational at minimum values of K^{dis} , i.e. in negative land forms. Higher values for K^{dis} will be reached for dumping waste on steeper slopes.

In the case when the volume of overburden is dumped on previously disturbed areas during previous mining activities or on existing embankment benches for internal waste dumping, then $K^{dis} = 0$ m²/m³, as no additional areas of the earth's surface are disturbed. By analogy with the method of prof. A.I. Arsentiev (Anachkov and Konstantinov, 1985) for determining the integral schedule of mining works $f(\Sigma P) = \Sigma V$, a similar function for the dumping works can be constructed, as in a coordinate system the volume of the overburden in swollen state for the dump building is compared with the area affected by it: $f(\Sigma V) = \Sigma S$.

Where ΣP , ΣV and ΣS is the general form for denoting the corresponding sums of volumes for ore, waste and required

dumping areas at reaching a certain stage of the mine's life (on an annual base or at the point of reaching a new bench).

During the construction of the embankment facility, for each stage of dumping a given volume of overburden, it can be approximately established what area will be disturbed by it. Two curves can be compared on the integrated schedule, corresponding to two principally opposite options of the embankment construction: 1) for $H \rightarrow \min$ (or $B \rightarrow \max$); 2) for $H \rightarrow \max$ (or $B \rightarrow \min$), where B is the required width of the benches for waste dumping.

In the first alternative, the embankment is built bench by bench, thus it is necessary to disturb the maximum amount of areas for the construction of each subsequent level. In the second case, smaller areas of the terrain are disturbed, as the volumes of overburden are dumped in order for the waste dump to reach its maximum feasible height, while at the same time the benches have the minimum required width for placing the necessary machines. In Figure 1 a schematic diagram of the two curves of the two alternatives for dump building is represented.

This diagram could also be represented as a table for more tough cases of terrain, where the dependence is not as smooth. Nevertheless, it proves that the waste dump construction technology is a major factor for this dependence.

In order to obtain better accuracy for the required dumping area during the stages of dumping, the embankment bench can be divided into u segments by the number of segments forming the shape of the m -th bench for dump alternative j . A necessary condition is that the segments should be linked to the technological sequence of the construction of the current embankment bench. Furthermore, each segment could be formed for reaching a certain height of the waste dump.

Figure 1. Dependence between the disturbed area and the waste volume for waste dump building

Nevertheless, the objective functions F_1 and F_2 acquire the form:

$$F_1 = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \sum_{l=1}^{u_k} \left\{ \left[\left(L_{ij} + \frac{K_{ijkl} \cdot h + (k-1) \cdot H}{\sin \arctg i_p} + \overline{L_{ijkl}} \right) \cdot \gamma_o \cdot P_{\tau p} + P_H \right] \cdot \left[K_{ijkl} \cdot V_{ijkl} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} V_{ijk'} \right] + \left[K_{ijkl}^{dis} \cdot K_{ijkl} \cdot V_{ijkl} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} K_{ijk'}^{dis} \cdot V_{ijk'} \right] \cdot (c_{dis} + c_{rec}) \right\} \cdot X_{ijkl}$$

$$F_2 = \sum_i^N S_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \sum_{l=1}^{u_k} \left[K_{ijkl}^{dis} \cdot K_{ijkl} \cdot V_{ijkl} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} K_{ijk'}^{dis} \cdot V_{ijk'} \right] \cdot X_{ijkl}$$

Whether solving the simpler version of the task or the option with the individual segments, it is necessary that the possible solutions meet each of the following limiting conditions:

$$1) \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} = 1 \quad A_{ij} = \{0;1\}$$

$$2) \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} X_{ijk} = 1 \quad X_{ijk} = \{0;1\}$$

$$2') \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \sum_{l=1}^{u_k} X_{ijkl} = 1 \quad X_{ijkl} = \{0;1\}$$

$$3) \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \left[K_{ijk} \cdot V_{ijk} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} V_{ijk'} \right] \cdot X_{ijk} = V_o \cdot K_{s.f.}$$

$$3') \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} A_{ij} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{m_j} \sum_{l=1}^{u_k} \left[K_{ijkl} \cdot V_{ijkl} + \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} V_{ijk'} \right] \cdot X_{ijkl} = V_o \cdot K_{s.f.}$$

$$4) 0 \leq K_{ijk} \leq 1 \quad (K_{ijk} \text{ is generated starting from 0 and gradually reaches 1 with a step for each alternative}).$$

Where V_o - volume of overburden, which is a subject to embankment, m^3 ;

$K_{s.f.}$ - swelling factor for the waste material (overburden).

For the calculation of the disturbed areas by means of the coefficients K_{ijk}^{dis} (or K_{ijkl}^{dis}) the following alternatives exist:

- For the purpose of performing approximate calculations, it is assumed that the dependence $f(\Sigma V) = \Sigma S$ is close to a linear one for each bench k (or each segment l for its corresponding bench k), i.e. K_{ijk}^{dis} is linear for each interval k to $k+1$ (or l to $l+1$ for each k) and is determined by the equation:

$$K_{ijk}^{dis} = \frac{S_{ijk}}{V_{ijk}}, m^2 / m^3 \quad \text{or} \quad K_{ijkl}^{dis} = \frac{S_{ijkl}}{V_{ijkl}}, m^2 / m^3$$

- An interpolation polynomial $P(\Sigma V) = \Sigma S$ with maximum degree $k-1$ (or $l-1$ for each k) is used, as K_{ijk}^{dis} is determined by the equation:

$$K_{ijk}^{hap} = \frac{P_{ijk}}{V_{ijk}}, m^2 / m^3 \quad \text{or} \quad K_{ijkl}^{hap} = \frac{P_{ijkl}}{V_{ijkl}}, m^2 / m^3$$

The Boolean variables A_{ij} and X_{ijk} (or X_{ijki}) express the branches in the decision tree on which the individual alternatives A_{ij} and the possible end positions for the embankment are located. By means of the method of random search and the subsequent generation of numbers in the admissible intervals for A_{ij} , X_{ijk} (or X_{ijki}) and K_{ijk} (or K_{ijki}) a set of solutions W is formed, representing different distribution of the volume of overburden for the individual embankment sites and obtaining embankments with different construction.

Each of the dumping solutions (DS) can be represented as a point with coordinates $DS_w (F_{1w}, F_{2w})$, where w is the sequential number of the solution. The computer generated solutions and their respective points determine the boundary of the Pareto-optimal solutions, the values of which dominate over the rest of the generated solutions. The solution at a given point $DS_w(F_{1w}, F_{2w})$ is considered to dominate the solution $DS_w''(F_{1w}'', F_{2w}'')$ when the implemented conditions are valid:

$$\begin{cases} F_{1w}' \leq F_{1w}'' \\ F_{2w}' \leq F_{2w}'' \end{cases}$$

Each of the points located on the Pareto boundary and each of the other points of the generated solutions are satisfying the system. From the obtained solutions at the Pareto boundary, depending on the difference in the disturbed areas between the solutions, the one that satisfies additionally introduced conditions, expressing the economic or environmental requirements, is selected.

Example of the algorithm in practice

A case study was made for a project for a metallic ore deposit. Two areas are taken into consideration and for each area two dump design alternatives are made. The bulk volume of waste for dumping is approximately 5 500 000 m³ (approximately 7 100 000 m³ after swelling).

Input data:

- $N = 2$ (feasible dumping areas);
 - $n_1 = 2$ and $n_2 = 2$ (alternatives for each dumping area);
 - $L_{tr1} = 1,1$ km;
 - $L_{tr2} = 1,7$ km;
 - $i_s = 10\%$;
 - $\gamma_o = 2,1$ t/m³;
 - $K_{s.f.} = 1,3$;
- The step which changes the values for K_{ijk} is 0.05.

Dumping area 1. Alternative 1:

- Average terrain slope: 12°
- Bench slope angle: 35°
- Bench height: 20 m
- Bench width: 15 m
- Number of benches: 3

Dumping area 1. Alternative 2:

- Average terrain slope: 12°
- Bench slope angle: 35°
- Bench height: 15 m
- Bench width: 10 m
- Number of benches: 4

Dumping area 2. Alternative 1:

- Average terrain slope: 7°
- Bench slope angle: 30°

- Bench height: 30 m
- Bench width: 15 m
- Number of benches: 1

Dumping area 2. Alternative 2:

- Average terrain slope: 7°
- Bench slope angle: 30°
- Bench height: 15 m
- Bench width: 10 m
- Number of benches: 2

For calculating K_{ijk}^{dis} the linear alternative is chosen.

Table 1 represents the dependence between the dumped volumes and the disturbed areas:

Table 1. Case study results

Area alternative i	Design alternative j	Bench number k	Waste volume, m ³ V _{ijk}	Total waste volume, m ³ Σ V _{ijk}	Disturbed area, m ² S _{ijk}	Total disturbed area, m ² Σ S _{ijk}	Disturbance factor, m ² /m ³ K ^{dis} _{ijk}
1	1	1	526317	526317	67623	67623	0.1284
1	1	2	1103980	1630297	56981	123604	0.0507
1	1	3	2921313	4551610	150454	274058	0.0515
1	2	1	320497	320497	56538	56538	0.1764
1	2	2	672629	993126	41015	97553	0.0610
1	2	3	990775	1983901	42156	138568	0.0425
1	2	4	2667709	4551610	136489	274057	0.0528
2	1	1	2886533	2886533	246165	246165	0.0853
2	2	1	499623	499623	68095	68095	0.1363
2	2	2	2235910	2735533	178070	246165	0.0900

Figure 2 represents the points of all the generated solutions, which fulfil the problem's requirements.

Dumping solutions

Figure 2. Dumping solutions for current case study

The dominant solutions for this case study are shown as the circled ones. The mining engineer has the option to decide whether less disturbed area is preferable for the specific project, or it is preferable to have less total costs.

Conclusions

The optimality of the obtained solution depends on the following prerequisites:

- the number and accuracy of the available dump design surfaces;
- the choice of the method for calculating the K_{ijk}^{dis} indicator;
- the size of the step through which the variable K_{ijk} (or K_{ijki}) takes values in the range [0; 1];
- the type of the construction technology planned for building the waste dump (determines the segment design for each bench).

The advantages of the method include:

- The solution found provides an opportunity for rational use of the areas within the concession border for the implementation of the waste dumping activities;
- This method significantly reduces (but does not eliminate) the subjective factor in choosing the location of the embankment and the shape of its structure;
- The solution of the problem can be represented as an algorithm and solved repeatedly with the help of software;
- The method can be applied for selective waste dumping, which requires different sets of feasible dumping areas for each type of waste (overburden) or diluted ore with contents lower than the cut-off grade.
- The method can also be applied for optimising the costs and the required areas for building ore stockpiles, although certain changes in the costs sum have to be made.

Disadvantages of the method include:

- The solutions found are suboptimal, i.e. they are optimal for the set of solutions W (which is a subset of the set of all possible solutions) and do not always coincide with the optimal solutions for the global set of solutions;
- In order to obtain a more accurate and optimal solution, it is necessary to design more alternatives for the waste dumps, as well as to design more of their segments surfaces, representing the different stages of their construction.

Opportunities for improvement:

- For obtaining even better results and optimising the shape of the dumps (incl. transport costs and disturbed areas, also), the costs for technical and biological reclamation could

be included in the target cost function, as well as the possibility for moving waste dumps in different time periods of the mine exploitation. In this way, the optimality of the solution is achieved in the long run until the final phase of the reclamation of the mine and its waste dump.

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